

Alcohol Consumption and the Risk of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Case Control Study in Uyo Metropolis, Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The association between alcohol intake and the risk of diabetes has not been consistent in many epidemiological studies. The authors attempted to find the association between the risk of type 2 diabetes and alcohol consumption in an age and sex matched case-control study between March and December 2016 among middle aged and elderly adults in Uyo Metropolis, Southern Nigeria. Cases were defined as 'known diabetics' and 'persons with FBS>126mg/dl or RBS> 140 mg/dl'. Controls were defined as 'persons who are not a known case of diabetes' and with 'FBS<126mg/dl or RBS<140mg/dl'. Alcohol consumption was assessed and classified into lifetime abstainers, former drinkers and current drinkers at various levels. There was a linear inverse relationship between alcohol intake and the risk of type 2 diabetes among the case group in this study. After adjustment for potential confounders, a decreased risk of diabetes was found in subjects who drank >21 drinks/week [O.R=1.52 (95%CI: 1.01, 1.91), 14.1 - 21 drinks/week [1.61 (95%CI: 0.92, 2.12)] and 7.1-14 drinks/week [O.R= 1.82 (95%CI: 1.66, 2.23)] when compared with those who drank ≤1 drink/week and the association with diabetes was not statistically significant. The risk of diabetes mellitus was reduced with consumption of higher quantities of alcohol. This highlights the probable protective effect of alcohol intake on the risk of diabetes mellitus. Prospective studies would be necessary to establish a causal relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: Alcohol, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 150 million individuals worldwide have diabetes mellitus, and due to factors such as population growth, aging, alcohol consumption, obesity, and sedentary lifestyles; the number, especially in developing countries, may double by 2025¹. The association between alcohol consumption and fasting serum glucose level (FSG) is inconsistent in epidemiologic studies^{2,3}. The relationship between alcohol intake and risk of type II diabetes has been examined in relatively few prospective studies⁴⁻¹³. Some studies report no association^{5,8} while others have suggested that heavy drinking is a risk factor

for diabetes^{6,7,12}. On the other hand, recent prospective studies suggest that light to moderate drinking may protect against the development of diabetes^{9,11,13}. This is consistent with observations that low to moderate amounts of alcohol intake increase insulin sensitivity¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and it is established that insulin resistance and hyper-insulinaemia play an important part in the aetiology of type II diabetes^{18,19}. This paper examines the association between alcohol consumption and the risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus among middle aged and elderly adults in Uyo metropolis, Southern Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Location

Akwa Ibom State is a state in Nigeria located on the southern part of the country lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E with a population of over 5 million people.

Study Design

This is an age (± 5 years) and sex matched case control study conducted between March and December 2016 among middle-aged and elderly adults in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Ethical approval was received from the Ethical Review Board of Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Health.

Sample

150 cases and 150 controls were selected using a house to house survey in the Aka Etinan axis of Uyo Metropolis. A maximum of three visits was made per case. Cases were defined as 'known diabetics' and 'persons with FBS > 126 mg/dl or RBS > 140 mg/dl'. Controls were defined as 'persons who are not a known case of diabetes' and with 'FBS < 126 mg/dl or RBS < 140 mg/dl'.

Respondents who were unwilling and/or unable to provide an informed consent were excluded. Respondents under 36 years were excluded. Persons who were critically ill or with other co morbidities were also excluded.

Study Instrument

The questionnaire was developed after a thorough literature review and further evaluation by experts in public health to ensure quality and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a test-retest reliability method with young adults (18-35 years) in Aka Etinan axis of Uyo Metropolis. The Pearson moment coefficient (r) was calculated. The coefficient 0.91 was determined.

They were interviewed using a structured interviewer-assisted questionnaire after signing an informed consent. Verbal consent was taken for those who could neither read nor write.

Measure

The variables were assessed as defined by Kao et al ²⁰.

Assessment of Alcohol consumption

Alcohol consumption was assessed using five questions. The following two questions were used to determine the current drinking status of the persons:

- "Do you presently drink alcoholic beverages?"
- "Have you ever consumed alcoholic beverages?"

Persons were classified as lifetime abstainers if they answered "no" to both questions. Persons who answered "no" to the first question and "yes" to the second question

were classified as former drinkers. Persons who answered "yes" to both questions were considered current drinkers.

Among current drinkers, the following three questions were used to determine the amount and type of alcoholic beverage consumed:

- "How many glasses of wine do you usually have per week (one glass containing 12% alcohol)?"
- "How many bottles or cans of beer do you usually have per week (one bottle containing 5% alcohol)?"
- "How many drinks of hard liquor do you usually have per week (one shot containing 40% alcohol)?"

For the primary analyses, ethanol (rather than a specific beverage) was the main independent variable. Weekly ethanol consumption was derived from the responses to the three beverage questions using the following conversion factors: half a glass contains 18 g of ethanol; one beer bottle contains 33 g of ethanol, and one shot of hard liquor contains 17.6 g of ethanol.

To reclassify current drinkers by the number of drinks (nonspecific to type of alcohol) consumed per week, we assumed one generic drink to be equal to 23 g of ethanol. Seven consumption groups were created:

- lifetime abstainers, former drinkers,
- current drinkers who consume <1 drink/week (reference group)
- current drinkers who consume 1.1–7 drinks/week,
- current drinkers who consume 7.1–14 drinks/week,
- current drinkers who consume 14.1–21 drinks/week, and current drinkers who consume more than 21 drinks/week.

For each beverage type, persons who identified themselves as current drinkers but reported an average weekly consumption of zero servings of that beverage were used as the reference group.

Information on age, gender, race, family history of diabetes, and education was obtained. A positive family history of diabetes was defined as having any of either biologic parent or a first degree relative with diabetes. Body mass index (weight (kg)/height (m)²) and waist/hip ratio were determined by anthropometric measurements. Measurements were made with the participants wearing light-weight, non-constricting underwear and no shoes. Waist and hip measurements were taken at the level of the umbilicus and the level of maximal protrusion of the gluteal muscles, respectively. Intrareader and interreader

correlations between repeated waist/hip ratio measures were 0.94 and 0.91, respectively ²¹.

Physical activity was assessed using a modified interviewer-administered version of the questionnaire developed by Baecke et al. ²². Results from the questionnaire concerning physical activity were pooled to a sport-related physical activity index with scores ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating the lowest level of activity and 5 the highest level. Total caloric intake was derived from a modified interviewer-administered version of the 61-item food frequency questionnaire developed by Willett et al. ²³.

Smoking status was categorized into never, former, and current smokers. Hypertension was defined by the presence of any of the following: 1) systolic blood pressure of ≥ 140 mmHg, 2) diastolic blood pressure of ≥ 90 mmHg, or 3) current use of antihypertensive medication.

Assessment of Diabetes

Diabetes mellitus was defined as the presence of any one of the following:

- 1) Fasting glucose of ≥ 7.0 mmol/L,
- 2) Non-fasting glucose of ≥ 11.1 mmol/L,
- 3) Current use of diabetic medication, or

4) A positive response to the question, “Has a doctor ever told you that you had diabetes (sugar in the blood)?”

Analysis

The questionnaires were carefully examined for correctness and completeness, coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 for Windows. Quantitative data generated from the study was presented in form of tables and analyzed as descriptive frequencies and percentages.

Pearson’s chi-square (X^2) was used to determine whether respondents in each alcohol consumption group differed significantly between the case and control groups. Logistic regression was used to examine association between the alcohol consumption groups and the case and control groups. Analysis was first conducted without covariates (using ordinal logistic regression), and later with covariates (using multinomial logistic regression).

Appropriate diagnostics to ensure that the data satisfied the proportional-odds assumption, necessary to conduct the logistic regression, was done.

P-value of less than 0.05 was accepted to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1: Means (SDs*) and Frequencies of selected Baseline Characteristics of 150 Case Participants (Male = 75, Female = 75) by Alcohol Consumption Group

Variables	Lifetime Abstainers	Former Drinkers	Current Drinkers by alcohol consumption group (drinks/week)				
			≤ 1	1.1-7.0	7.1-14	14.1-21	>21
No (%)	48(32.0)	18(12.0)	41(27.3)	32(21.3)	6(4.0)	4(2.6)	1(1.5)
Age ¹	56.3(5.2)	54.1(5.5)	55.7(5.8)	56.1(5.1)	50.4(5.7)	51.1(5.2)	52.4(5.6)
Gender							
-Male	19(25.3)	7(9.3)	25(33.3)	24(32.0)	4(5.3)	3(4.0)	1(1.3)
-Female	29(38.7)	11(14.7)	16(21.3)	8(10.7)	2(2.7)	1(1.3)	0(0.0)
Education							
-Primary	8.8	10.7	7.0	19.2	17.9	18.1	28.0
-Secondary	44.1	42.4	49.5	41.9	46.2	49.8	51.4
-Tertiary	47.1	46.9	42.5	40.4	35.9	32.1	20.6
Family history of DM	31.6	30.8	28.4	27.6	27.4	28.1	28.4
Body Mass Index ¹	27.3(6.34)	28.5(4.45)	26.4(5.67)	25.2(5.83)	25.6(6.01)	25.9(5.91)	26.7(5.65)
Waist/Hip Ratio ¹	0.87(0.089)	0.910(0.085)	0.874(0.088)	0.860(0.078)	0.890(0.082)	0.901(0.088)	0.991(0.084)
Energy Intake	1,599(546)	1,618(489)	1,581(562)	1,478(467)	1,654(523)	1,765(595)	1,891(477)
Physical activity	2.61(0.69)	2.51(0.65)	2.39(0.72)	2.28(0.63)	2.26(0.68)	2.30(0.71)	2.15(0.66)
Smoking							
-Current	12.7	24.4	31.2	43.8	56.2	58.4	60.2
-Former	11.2	19.1	30.7	20	9.6	5.9	3.0
-Never	76.1	56.5	38.1	36.2	34.2	35.7	36.8
Hypertension	40.6	38.5	31.2	34.3	34.7	30.6	33.9

Serum Glucose ¹	10.42(0.45)	10.47(0.42)	10.51(0.46)	10.49(0.44)	10.11(0.48)	10.67(0.41)	10.81(0.48)
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*SD = standard deviation; 1 = Mean

Table 2: Means (SDs*) and Frequencies of selected baseline characteristics of 150 Control Participants (Male = 75, Female = 75) by Alcohol Consumption Group

Variables	Lifetime Abstainers	Former Drinkers	Current Drinkers by alcohol consumption group (drinks/week)				
			≤1	1.1-7.0	7.1-14	14.1-21	>21
No (%)	50(33.3)	21(14.0)	38(25.4)	30(20.4)	5(3.3)	3(2.0)	3(2.0)
Age ¹	55.6(5.3)	54.8(5.4)	55.1(5.1)	56.6(5.3)	51.8(5.5)	52.1(5.2)	52.2(5.8)
Gender (%)							
-Male	21(28.0)	12(16.0)	20(26.6)	24(32.0)	4(5.3)	2(2.7)	2(2.7)
-Female	34(45.3)	9(12.0)	18(24.0)	6(8.0)	1(1.3)	1(1.3)	1(1.3)
Education							
-Primary	6.3	8.3	9.4	15.4	18.8	21.2	26.3
-Secondary	51.6	39.7	43.1	38.1	42.5	40.2	50.1
-Tertiary	42.1	52.0	47.5	46.5	38.7	32.1	23.6
Family history of DM	11.6	26.6	10.8	10.2	17.3	8.6	7.4
Body Mass Index ¹	24.2(4.13)	23.9(4.54)	24.8(4.38)	22.9(4.01)	23.6(4.56)	24.9(4.19)	25.8(4.67)
Waist/Hip Ratio ¹	0.810(0.081)	0.830(0.084)	0.860(0.082)	0.880(0.079)	0.890(0.084)	0.920(0.088)	0.910(0.083)
Energy Intake	1,418(473)	1,5699(512)	1,473(548)	1,569(562)	1,612(482)	1,684(494)	1,793(512)
Physical activity	2.34(0.71)	2.45(0.75)	2.49(0.71)	2.57(0.70)	2.68(0.74)	2.21(0.71)	2.20(0.73)
Smoking							
-Current	10.4	22.4	29.2	33.8	46.6	47.4	51.2
-Former	3.2	3.1	22.6	29.0	17.0	16.9	11.1
-Never	86.4	74.5	48.2	37.2	36.4	35.7	37.7
Hypertension	26.4	47.8	46.3	44.2	38.7	40.2	36.9
Serum Glucose ¹	6.53(0.47)	6.74(0.49)	6.25(0.45)	6.74(0.47)	6.36(0.45)	6.76(0.46)	6.74(0.48)

*SD = standard deviation, 1= mean

Table 3: Weighted Multivariate Association (95% confidence intervals) for Case and Control Groups and Alcohol Consumption groups

	Case		Control	
	Model 1*	Model 2**	Model 1	Model 2
>21	1.52 ^{NS} (1.01, 1.91)	1.41 ^{NS} (1.27, 2.34)	0.72 ^{NS} (0.23, 1.12)	0.61 ^{NS} (0.15, 1.62)
14.1-21	1.61 ^{NS} (0.92, 2.12)	1.53 ^{NS} (1.05, 1.97)	0.91 ^{NS} (0.25, 1.15)	0.89 ^{NS} (0.48, 1.64)
7.1-14	1.82 ^{NS} (1.66, 2.23)	1.65 ^{NS} (0.87, 2.11)	1.19 ^{NS} (0.41, 1.55)	1.01 ^{NS} (0.32, 1.82)
1.1-7.0	2.99 ^b (2.15, 3.34)	1.98 ^a (1.45, 2.86)	1.34 ^{NS} (1.16, 2.69)	1.23 ^{NS} (0.68, 1.95)
≤1	1.0(reference)	1.0(reference)	1.0(reference)	1.0(reference)
Former Drinkers	3.01 ^b (2.46, 3.55)	2.64 ^b (1.23, 2.99)	1.56 ^{NS} (1.04, 1.89)	1.56 ^{NS} (1.09, 2.08)

Lifetime Abstainers	3.09 ^b (2.78, 3.77)	2.82 ^b (1.11, 2.37)	1.59 ^{NS} (0.61, 2.28)	1.41 ^{NS} (1.07, 2.81)
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NS = Not significant; a = P value ≤ 0.05 ; b = P value ≤ 0.01

* Model 1 adjusted for gender (male vs. female), age (≤ 50 vs. 50.1–54.9 vs. 55–59.9 vs. ≥ 60), education (primary vs. secondary vs. tertiary), family history of diabetes (binary), body mass index (quartiles), waist/hip ratio (quartiles), physical activity score (continuous), total energy intake (quartiles), smoking history (never vs. former vs. current), and history of hypertension (binary) using multinomial logistic regression.

** Model 2 = model 1 + Serum Glucose level

a) Baseline Characteristics

32 per cent of case and 33.3 per cent of control participants reported that they were lifetime abstainers. 56 per cent of case and 52.7 per cent of control identified themselves as current drinkers, of which 65.5% and 48.1% of current drinkers reported an average weekly consumption of ≤ 1 drink/week in the case and control groups respectively.

Both lifetime abstainers and former drinkers tended to be overweight (mean BMI being 27.3 and 28.5 respectively) in the case group but not in the control group (mean BMI being 24.2 and 23.9 respectively). There was also a greater proportion of positive family history of diabetes and hypertension among lifetime abstainers and former drinkers in the case group than in the control group. Among current drinkers, total caloric intake and prevalence of hypertension were positively associated with alcohol consumption in the case group, while educational level, family history of diabetes, and body mass index were inversely associated with alcohol consumption both case and control groups.

Persons who drank more than 14 drinks per week had a noticeably higher waist/hip ratio in the control group. There was no pattern for this variable in the case group. Total caloric intake and less physical activity were positively associated with increased alcohol intake. Smoking and alcohol consumption were highly associated in both case and control groups. Random serum glucose level was slightly positively associated with alcohol consumption among current drinkers.

Among current drinkers, men were drinking more drinks per week than women, with the amount

consumed by men slightly higher for each consumption group. 5.3 percent and 5.4 per cent of men drank >14 drinks/week in the case and control groups respectively. 1.3 per cent and 2.6 per cent of women drank >14 drinks/week in the case and control groups respectively.

Men who drank >14 drinks/week had the highest waist/hip ratio and energy intake and the lowest physical activity score in the control group while men who were former drinkers and who had more than 21 drinks per week in the case group had the highest waist/hip ratio and energy intake and the lowest physical activity score. The proportions of current smokers and persons with hypertension were also highest in men who had >21 drinks per week.

b) Association of alcohol consumption and Risk of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

To determine the independent relation of alcohol consumption and the risk of type 2 diabetes, we adjusted for gender, age, level of education, family history of diabetes, body mass index, waist/hip ratio, physical activity, total caloric intake, smoking history, and history of hypertension using multinomial logistic regression. There was an inverse association between alcohol consumption and the case group and it was statistically significant for lifetime abstainers [AOR = 3.09 (2.78, 3.77); P value < 0.01], former drinkers [AOR = 3.01 (2.46, 3.55); P value < 0.01], and those who take 1.1-7 drinks per week [AOR = 2.99 (2.15, 3.34); P value < 0.01].

There were no significant associations for alcohol consumption groups in the control groups.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we observed an inverse association between alcohol consumption and the risk of diabetes among the case group and no association between the two variables in the control group after adjusting for confounding factors. Intake of greater than 7 drinks per week was associated with a lower risk of diabetes mellitus in the case group. This relationship was also sustained when the serum glucose level (mmol/L) was also taken into consideration after adjusting the potential confounders (Table 3).

A number of epidemiological studies have reported the protective effects of moderate drinking on the

development of diabetes mellitus^{24, 25, 26, 27}. Persons with a larger daily alcohol intake had a lower risk of developing type 2 diabetes compared to total abstainers. One meta-analysis with data from 13 cohorts showed an overall risk reduction (RR) of 30% in persons of both genders drinking 5 - 30g of alcohol daily compared to abstainers and people with a daily consumption above 30g alcohol²⁸. Another meta-analysis found a risk reduction of developing type 2 diabetes of approximately 30% by a daily consumption of 6 - 48 g of alcohol²⁹. In this study, there was no difference in the risk of diabetes mellitus between moderate and heavy drinkers. However, a meta-analysis of prospective

observational studies has reported that heavy drinkers (>48 g alcohol daily), have a relative risk of type 2 diabetes corresponding to that of non-consumers²⁹.

There was a linear inverse relationship between alcohol intake and the risk of type 2 diabetes among the case group in this study. Other studies have found a linear inverse relationship association between alcohol intake and incidence of type 2 diabetes³⁰. In Nurses' Health Study, alcohol intake was associated with a lower risk of type 2 diabetes compared to a reduced or no intake³¹. In the 12-year prospective Health Professionals Follow-Up Study, there was a similar inverse association between alcohol intake and type 2 diabetes in males. The stratum with the highest intake (above 50 g alcohol daily) had a relative risk for type 2 diabetes of 0.60 compared to abstainers^{32,33}.

The prospective Physician's Health Study also showed that consumption of alcohol in men has an inverse linear association with the incidence of type 2 diabetes³⁴. Also, an Australian study including both genders revealed an inverse dose-response curve in women, while no association was seen in men³⁵. However, not all studies find an inverse association between alcohol intake and risk of type 2 diabetes. Some studies have found no association between alcohol intake and incidence of type 2 diabetes³⁶.

Some studies have reported a positive association between alcohol intake and incidence of type 2 diabetes in men³⁷. A study in Japan reported that the positive association between alcohol intake and incidence of type 2 diabetes is BMI-dependent. It also reported that both moderate and heavy alcohol consumption increase the risk of type 2 diabetes in men with a relatively low BMI, whereas moderate alcohol consumption protects men with a higher BMI from developing type 2 diabetes.

The type of alcoholic beverage and the drinking pattern might affect the association between the alcohol intake and the incidence of type 2 diabetes. A study reported that binge drinking increases the risk of type 2 diabetes in women but not in men compared to consumption of the same amount of alcohol over a longer period of time³⁸. Another study found that consumption of more than 210g alcohol in 1-3 days increases the risk of type 2 diabetes five times, but consuming the same amount of alcohol distributed over a week does not influence the risk³⁵.

A study reported that frequent consumption of small amounts of alcohol (preferably at least 5 days a week) has the most pronounced inverse association with risk of type 2 diabetes compared to the same amount

alcohol taken once³². The impact of the type of alcoholic beverage is controversial. In other studies^{30,32}, the liquor type did not play a role. This indicates that the impact on the risk of developing type 2 diabetes is mainly an ethanol-mediated effect. It has been found that there is an increased risk of type 2 diabetes in men who drink heavily, with spirits being more deleterious than wine and beer³⁸. Also, in the Melbourne Collaborative Cohort Study it was seen that consumption of wine apparently lowers the risk of type 2 diabetes, while there is no association to consumption of beer and spirits³⁵.

Some mechanisms have been postulated for the protective effect of alcohol on diabetes mellitus to include the alcohol-induced improvement of insulin sensitivity^{41,42} mediated via the inflammatory pathway or via intermediary metabolism⁴³. Also, plasma adiponectin levels has been seen to be significantly higher in men and women consuming alcohol⁴².

There were some limitations in this study. Alcohol consumption and drinking frequency were evaluated by questionnaire. This raises the likelihood of recall bias in the course of the data collection. The study could not differentiate subjects with type 1 diabetes mellitus from subjects with type 2 diabetes mellitus. This raises the likelihood of the association to be confounded with autoimmune diabetes mellitus. Also, the cross sectional nature of the study might not allow us to establish a causal relationship between alcohol intake and the risk of diabetes mellitus. Data on dietary factors were not available, so other low-risk lifestyle behaviors might have influenced our results. This study did not evaluate drinking pattern. Participants may have underreported their consumption level.

This study had its strengths. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first community based case control study that is evaluating the association between alcohol intake and the risk of diabetes mellitus in Nigeria. It has been suggested that persons who are not currently drinking may be abstaining from drinking alcohol because of health reasons, and that the use of such persons as the reference group could potentially lead to an artifactual protective effect of alcohol use. Hence, we created a distinction between current drinkers, former drinkers and abstainers. Furthermore, the reference group was those who took at most 1 alcoholic drink per week but were neither former drinkers nor abstainers. This removed the confounding of observational association between alcohol consumption and risk of altered glucose metabolism.

CONCLUSION

The risk of diabetes mellitus was reduced with consumption of higher quantities of alcohol. This highlights the probable protective effect of alcohol intake on the risk

of diabetes mellitus. Prospective studies would be necessary to establish a causal relationship between the two variables.

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